

Classical Mechanics as a Subset of Quantum Mechanics?

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Classical mechanics was developed in the 1600s and is considered a complete theory in that it matches observables in the macroscopic world. In the 1920s, however, it was found that different mechanical rules seem to apply to the electron in an atom.

In this note we try to argue that classical mechanics is a subset of quantum mechanics i.e. it is based on partial information or the dropping of information. In (1) we noted that a classical spatial density $Cdx/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity, is sometimes presented in the literature (2). This expression is proportional to dt associated with a fixed length dx so the density is a relative one. If one considers two bound classical systems (a particle in a box) with different constant speeds (in the interior) then dt is different for each, but $Cdx/v(x)$ does not distinguish. Thus we argue that information has been lost. The higher v particle not only has a higher impulse, but an increased frequency and we argued in (1) that quantum mechanics takes note of this extra frequency by increasing the number of crests associated with higher constant velocities.

In this note, we point out that quantum mechanics itself is linked to the dropping of information. If one considers free particle wavefunctions $W(x)$ for different momenta (i.e. velocities if m_0 is the same), one has $\exp(ip_1 x)$, $\exp(ip_2 x)$ etc. These clearly have different information. They describe direction, but more importantly they have an associated wavelength proportional to $1/p$. $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)=\text{constant}$ and so this information, which is physical, is lost. $P(x)$ is related to the question: What is the probability for a particle to be at x ? If one considers $\cos(px)$ as a nonlocal spatial distribution which shows motion i.e. negative and positive parts of $\cos(px)$, then $\sin(px)$ is a spatially shifted distribution which helps to indicate direction, but also shows that all x points are the same. One has a peak of $\cos(px)$ at $x=0$ and a lower value at $x=\delta$, but due to the motion, the peak may later be at δ just like a classical wave. This is what $W^*(x)W(x)=\text{constant}$ captures. It shows that even though $\cos(px)$ maps to x in a certain way with $\sin(px)$ in an extra dimension, overall the free particle has no preference for one x point versus another.

There are two points we wish to make. First, classical mechanics seems to be based on $P(x)$ i.e. it drops information about a wavelength. Space is broken into tiny dx units and the particle has a constant velocity in each even if it is accelerating. This is the Newtonian picture and leads to $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ or $pp/2m + V(x) = E$. This information, however, is contained completely in quantum mechanics because for a bound state with $V(x)$ one has: $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W + V(x) = E_n$.

$-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$ is exactly $KE(x)$ classical.

Quantum mechanics, however, displays more information than the classical picture. For example, only certain E_n are allowed and $W^*(x)W(x)$ leads to a spatial density which does not appear in classical mechanics. This leads to a second point. $\exp(ipx)$ contains information about a wavelength which is lost if one only considers $P(x)$ for a free particle. If there is an interaction (two electrons shifted in space, a $V(x)$ or a single or double slits etc) $\exp(ipx)$ acts like a probability and adds in OR or interaction situations. In such a case the information regarding the wavelength becomes physically crucial. In other words for an interaction this information does not drop out as it does in the classical scenario of $pp/2m + V(x) = E$. Thus we argue that

classical mechanics is a subset of quantum mechanics. Wavelengths are tiny in the macroscopic world and so are simply not observed, allowing the subset scenario of $\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) = E$ (nonrelativistic) to be an excellent approximation. Indeed for every energy level of a quantum bound state this relationship also holds. It is the spatial density which is altered.

Classical Mechanics

Classical mechanics is based on breaking space into equally spaced dx regions and considering constant $v(x)$ motion to first order within each dx even if the particle is accelerating. The particle is considered to be a point. This approach, i.e. Newton's equations $\frac{dp}{dt} = F$ which is equivalent to $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{p^2}{2m} = -\frac{d}{dx} V(x)$ $dx = F dx$ or $\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) = E$ describes macroscopic motion very well nonrelativistically.

A paradox, however, emerges if one considers the use of $Cdx/v(x)$ as classical spatial density (as in (2)). For fixed dx , dt is the measure of density, but this gives a relative density scenario. If one has a particle in a box with m_0, p_1 and later with m_0, p_2 then dt is clearly different, but $Cdx/v(x)$ is the same for both. Thus $P(x) = Cdx/v(x)$ cannot distinguish between the two physically different scenarios and we argued in (1) this suggests incompleteness. p_1 and p_2 represent different impulses, but also different frequencies. In an impulse picture, one should distinguish the frequencies of p_1 and p_2 we argue. This is exactly what quantum mechanics allows, but classical mechanics doesn't.

Quantum Particle in a Box with Infinite Walls

A quantum particle in a box has a wavefunction of $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}i (\exp(i \text{pave } x) - \exp(-i \text{pave } x))$. This is linked to the free particle wavefunction or dynamic probability of $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ not only contains information about momentum p , direction ($\exp(ipx)$ differs from $\exp(-ipx)$), but also provides information about the crucial nonlocal feature of wavelength proportional to $1/p$. It is this feature which is missing from classical mechanics as $\exp(ipx)$ is also associated with a particle with momentum p and kinetic energy $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ which are both completely classical (nonrelativistic).

We argued in (1) that $W(x) = \exp(ipx)$ is linked to spatial density through $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$. If a particle has p_1 and m_0 , its impulse is related to p_1 and its frequency to v_1 . If the particle has a different p_2 (say greater) its impulse is larger and so is its v_2 and frequency. We argued that an impulse density picture should describe this spatially. Thus frequency must be described spatially so there should be more crests for p_1 than p_2 . In fact for the particle in a box $p = n \frac{3.14}{L}$ and as n increases by 1, the number of crests/troughs also increases by 1. Thus a physically accurate picture of constant motion should include a set of crests/troughs, but classical mechanics does not.

In (1) we argued that $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ represents two spatially shifted probability distributions in order to show the direction of motion. $\cos(px)$ shows crests/troughs linked to a wavelength of $1/p$. The negative portions of $\cos(px)$ show motion i.e. wavelike behaviour, but are not enough to demonstrate the direction of motion. One requires a shifted distribution in a second dimension i.e. $i \sin(px)$ for this. At the same time, due to motion one should have $P(x) = \text{constant}$ because all x points are the same from the point of view of constant velocity. This

result loses all information about p . In particular, $\cos(px)$ shows a peak at $x=0$, $2\pi/3.14$ etc i.e special x points, but because of motion one expects that overall these x points are not special at all. Thus the extra information contained in $\exp(ipx)$ must somehow collapse to yield a $P(x)$ with no crest information. This is what occurs with $P(x)=\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$. One, however, must realize that information is lost i.e. one no longer is aware of the physically present wavelength. How is this possible? The definition of $P(x)$ i.e the question: What is the probability for a free particle to be at any x ? does not require this information. Thus $P(x)$ is an incomplete physical picture, but it is the answer to the question.

Classical Mechanics as an Incomplete Picture

Classical mechanics seems to use the incomplete picture of $P(x)=\text{constant}$ from $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)=\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$. All information about p as a wavelength is lost, but if the particle is considered to be a point, this does not seem to be a big problem. The crucial question seems to be: What about dynamics?

For a bound quantum particle, dynamics are given by:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2W}{dx^2} / W + V(x) = E_n \quad ((1))$$

The first term on the LHS is $KE(x)$ classical thus one has $p^2/2m + V(x) = E_n$ which is exactly the classical mechanical result. The two differences are that E_n is discrete and that $W^*(x)W(x)$ creates a density of crests. If one cannot observe these crests because they are so tiny at a microscopic level and E_n 's are very close together, then the quantum rms scenario and classical mechanics are the same. Dynamically ((1)) show no difference. There are cases in quantum mechanics, however, where the wavelength information is important, namely interactions.

Wavelength in Quantum Mechanics

If $\exp(ipx)$ is considered to be a dynamic probability, one may see that even though $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ washes out wavelength information, this information is retained if interactions occur. For example if one compares two shifted identical quantum particles one has:

$$W(x) = \exp(ipx) + \exp(ip(x+\delta)) \quad ((2))$$

In such a case, $W^*(x)W(x)$ reveals a density which is not a constant i.e. reflects the wavelengths.

Similar considerations occur for single slit diffraction, two slit interference and interactions with $V(x)$ in a bound state. For a bound state, one has:

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

Thus much interference occurs to create an overall $W(x)$ with its own set of crests and troughs of different heights and spacing. Thus the idea of crests/troughs associated with an impulse

picture still holds. Even in such a case the dynamics are classical for a given E_n i.e. $p_{rms}(x)$ $p_{rms}(x)/2m + V(x) = E_n$. There is, however, a physical spatial density (which is measurable) of $W^*(x)W(x)$ which is not constant as in the $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ case.

Thus we argue that overall classical mechanics is a subset of quantum mechanics which drops information in the same way that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = \text{constant}$ does.

Conclusion

We argue that classical mechanics is a subset of quantum mechanics which shows correct dynamics for a bound particle, but loses information about spatial densities. For example, $P(x)=Cdx/v(x)$ which is classical, treats dt as proportional to spatial density. $P(x)$, however, cannot distinguish between constant p_1 and p_2 . They, however, have different dt i.e. not only is the impulse different, but the frequencies as well. We argued in (1) that an impulse density picture should show the increased frequency spatially. This is exactly what $\cos(px)$ from a quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ does. In other words, due to impulse considerations, physically there is a nonlocal situation of $\cos(px)$ crests/troughs. If one asks the question: What is the probability for the particle to be a $P(x)$, then the fact that $\cos(px)$ has a peak at $x=0$ is not important. Motion should treat all x points as the same. Thus one needs to bring in motion. $\cos(px)$ partially shows motion by having positive and negative portions like a classical wave, but these don't indicate direction and don't remove information about the wavelength. One needs two shifted distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ in two dimensions to allow for this i.e. $\cos(px) + i \sin(px) = \exp(ipx)$. Thus $P(x)=\text{constant}$ which loses physical information. We argue that classical mechanics is based on this partial information scenario. Indeed even quantum mechanics of a free particle allows for this loss as $\exp(-i p_1 x) \exp(i p_1 x)$ and $\exp(-i p_2 x) \exp(i p_2 x)$ are both constant.

Dynamically losing information about a wavelength does not change matters as classically one has: $p^2/2m + V(x) = E$ and quantum mechanically $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W + V(x) = E_n$. For a given E_n , $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$ is exactly $KE(x) = p_{rms}(x)p_{rms}(x)/2m$. No dynamical information is lost except that E_n is discrete. If E_n 's are very close together, this discreteness would not be noticed. If wavelengths are also tiny, they would not be noticed in the macroscopic world unless very careful experiments were done.

There are cases, however, where the wavelength is essential, namely in interactions. If $\exp(ipx)$ is treated as a dynamic probability, then it adds in OR situations. Thus for two shifted identical free particles, single slit diffraction, two slit interference or a bound wavefunction $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ the interference effects create a new spatial impulse density with its own frequency of crests and troughs (which in the bound case may have different heights). In such a case $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ is not a constant as in the free particle scenario.

Thus we conclude that classical mechanics is a theory based on a subset of the full quantum information which includes wavelengths.

References

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